

Investigation of the effect of atherosclerotic plaque location on the progression of luminal stenosis in carotids.

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Abstract The carotid artery disease is a major cause of mortality worldwide, urging the need for a change in the diagnosis and treatment procedure. To this end, any computational techniques are now being utilized towards improving the state-of-the-art diagnosis methods. In this work, a computational model describing the plaque growth process is implemented to 5 patient carotid segments, to predict their future plaque regions, lumen stenoses, as well as the evaluation of the plaque rupture risk. The simulated geometries are then utilized towards the investigation of the effect of plaque location on hemodynamics and the progression of luminal stenosis. The results indicate a strong correlation of plaque location to luminal stenosis progression, implying that curved arterial segments are more prone to plaque formation and progression.

Keywords Carotid Artery Disease; Plaque Growth Modeling; Plaque Location; Atherosclerosis Progression.

1 Introduction

Despite the multitude of studies on the carotid artery disease, it still remains a prevalent cause of death, urging the need of better diagnosis and treatment methods. The carotid artery disease originates from atherosclerosis, which is a disease identified by the plaque presence within the arteries, causing their narrowing and stiffening, and leading to the reduction of the brain's blood supply, which is a major cause of strokes or transient ischemic attacks (TIA). Histological analyses of atherosclerotic plaques proved the existence of cholesterol, calcium, fibrous tissue and other cellular debris within them, while the plaque composition is a means towards their discrimination into eight different types according to the American Heart Association [1].

The preventive methods of atherosclerosis concern either the regulation of the diet and exercise program, or the provision of medication, which lower blood lipids. In case of an ischemic event, the treatment methods include medication or/and surgery. The initial treatment includes the provision of medication for the breaking of clots (intravenous tissue plasminogen activator (tPA)), as well as, for the restoration of breathing, heart rate and blood pressure. However, in case tPA has no effect, clots can be surgically removed up to 24 hours after the onset of stroke symptoms [2].

However, the recent technological and biological advances affect the prevention and treatment strategy of the carotid artery disease. Even though the underlying biological process of the atherosclerotic plaque generation is very complex, over the past century, high serum lipids, smoking, diabetes and obesity have been identified as the major risk factors of atherosclerosis [2],[3]. On the other hand, over the last years, several studies have attempted to predict the atherosclerotic plaque growth using computational techniques.

According to a representative plaque growth model [4], the atherosclerotic process initiates with the effect of the flow-induced shear stress on the endothelial membrane. More specifically, in areas of low shear stresses, the endothelial function is altered increasing the endothelial permeability and leading to the abnormal accumulation of low-density lipoproteins (LDL) within the arterial wall. The free radicals of the arterial wall oxidize the infiltrated LDL, initiating an inflammatory response by the production of cytokines. The inflammatory mediators (cytokines) attract monocytes and T-cells, which are the basic cells of the immune system. Monocytes differentiate into macrophages by specific cytokines and become activated under the effect of the T-cells in order to uptake the oxidized LDL, that lead to the formation of the foam cells. Foam cells are the main component of fatty streaks. Moreover, the T-cell secreted cytokines cause the proliferation and differentiation of contractile smooth muscle cells (SMCs) into synthetic smooth muscle cells which secrete collagen to restore the inflammatory area. Overall, some of the basic plaque species, such as foam cells,

synthetic smooth muscle cells and collagen, are multiplied, increasing the wall thickness, while reducing the lumen area [5].

Over the past two decades, several models have been presented attempting to predict the atherosclerotic plaque progression. However, most of these studies utilized idealized 1D or 2D arterial geometries [6], while only a few proof-of-concept studies are based on realistic human arterial geometries [5], [7]–[12]

The scope of this study is to investigate the effect of plaque location on hemodynamics as well as, on the progression of luminal stenosis using a state-of-the-art model for the prediction of atherosclerotic plaque progression. In our approach we utilized 5 realistic human 3D reconstructed carotid arterial segments with different plaque locations and predicted the plaque progression. Two specific categories of plaque location were examined. The first one includes plaques in areas within straight carotid segments, while the second one includes plaques in areas within curved carotid segments. In both cases, plaques progress towards the direction of the blood flow, however, a higher progression rate is observed in the luminal stenosis of curved carotid segments, as opposed to the straight ones.

2 Materials & Methods

The patient MRI (magnetic resonance imaging) data are 3D reconstructed using a novel 3D reconstruction tool [13]. The reconstructed geometries along with the clinical data of each patient are used as input to the plaque growth model, which is performed in a 4-step procedure. The first step includes a steady-state simulation of the blood flow resulting in the evaluation of the WSS (wall shear stresses) distribution on the endothelium. The resulted flow-induced endothelial pressure is used as an initial condition to an arterial deformation model to evaluate the arterial wall strain distribution. Both distributions of WSS and wall strain are used as input to the next step, which is the simulation of the mass transport and the interactions within the arterial wall. During this step, equations are solved which account for the species dynamics, resulting to the evaluation of the plaque-induced strain distribution within the arterial wall. Finally, an arterial deformation structural analysis is performed using the strain distribution as an initial condition, which provides the final wall thickening and lumen stenosis.

2.1 Dataset

5 human carotid arteries have been employed for model development and validation. The dataset included patients' magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) data, as well as their corresponding clinical data (Blood LDL, Blood HDL, Blood Glucose, Hematocrit, Systolic & Diastolic Blood Pressure, Mass Flow Rate). Each

patient enrolled in the TAXINOMISIS clinical study (www.clinicaltrials.gov; ID: NCT03495830) provided written informed consent, and the study has received ethical committees' approval.

2.2 3D Reconstruction of carotid arteries and their plaque components

The reconstruction algorithm of the carotid arterial geometries utilizes a series of magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) modalities, including ToF, T1w, T2w and PD series. More specifically, the reconstruction of the lumen domain of the 3D model is based on the ToF series, while the reconstruction of the arterial wall and the plaques is based on the fusion of the T1w, T2w and PD series. Finally, the centerlines of the three resulting models are aligned to constitute the final arterial model (Fig 1).

The 3D reconstruction algorithm includes a novel methodology and comprises of three steps:

- a) Segmentation of the region of interest: The segmentation of all domains is based on three deep learning models (UNET), which were trained using two experts' annotations of 485 tuples of ToF, T1w, T2w and PD images from 42 different patients.
- b) 3D level set: A morphological operator is applied to the 3D volume of the stacked 2D segmented frames to produce the 3D surface model.
- c) 3D meshing: The marching cubes algorithm is applied to the 3D surface model, resulting to the final reconstructed arterial model.

Fig. 1 A case example of the baseline (left) and the follow-up (right) of a carotid arterial segment.

2.3 Simulation of atherosclerotic plaque progression

Plaque growth simulation was performed by modeling the major biological processes of atherosclerosis, which is performed in a 4-step modeling procedure, using several differential equations as previously described in detail [5], [12].

2.3.1 1st step – Blood flow

Initially, a steady state simulation of the luminal blood flow is performed using the Navier-Stokes equations considering a laminar, incompressible and Newtonian flow [5], [14].

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} (\rho U_i U_j) = -\frac{\partial P}{\partial x_j} - \frac{\partial \tau_{ij}}{\partial x_i}, \quad (1)$$

$$\text{where, } \tau_{ij} = -\mu \left(\frac{\partial U_j}{\partial x_i} + \frac{\partial U_i}{\partial x_j} + \frac{2}{3} \delta_{ij} \mu \frac{\partial U_k}{\partial x_k} \right), \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{D\rho}{Dt} + \frac{\partial(\rho \mathbf{K} \cdot \mathbf{U})_i}{\partial x_i} = 0, \quad (3)$$

where, ρ is the blood density, U is the blood velocity, P is the pressure, τ is the shear stress, μ is the dynamic viscosity
Blood flow in lumen is conditioned by Eq. 4-6.

$$\overrightarrow{\text{mass flow rate}}_{\text{inlet}} = \text{patient specific (kg/s)} \quad (4)$$

$$P_{\text{outlet}} = \text{patient specific (Pa)}, \quad (5)$$

$$\frac{\partial U}{\partial n_{\text{endothelium}}} = 0, \quad (6)$$

2.3.2 2nd step – Flow-induced deformation of the arterial wall.

The second step of our analysis considers the flow-induced strain to the arterial wall. To evaluate the arterial wall strain distribution a linear stress-strain equation is employed.

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \mathbf{D}\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}. \quad (7)$$

where, $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ is the tensor of the structural stress, D is the arterial wall's elasticity modulus and $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$ is the tensor of the structural stress.

A frictionless support is applied to the adventitia and the arterial wall side areas.

$$\frac{\partial \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}{\partial n_{\text{adventitia}}} = 0, \quad (8)$$

$$\frac{\partial \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}{\partial n_{\text{arterial wall side areas}}} = 0, \quad (9)$$

2.3.3 3rd step – Atherosclerotic process

The third step includes the modelling of the main mechanisms of plaque formation [5], [14]. The species transport is influenced by the transmural flow of plasma in the arterial wall, which is modeled by the modified Navier-Stokes equations, which account for the arterial wall's porosity.

$$\rho \gamma \frac{\partial U_j}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} (\rho (\mathbf{K} \cdot \mathbf{U})_i U_j) = -\gamma \frac{\partial P}{\partial x_j} - \frac{\partial \tau_{ij}}{\partial x_i} + \gamma S_M, \quad (12)$$

$$\text{where, } \tau_{ij} = -\mu_{\text{plasma}} \left(\frac{\partial U_j}{\partial x_i} + \frac{\partial U_i}{\partial x_j} + \frac{2}{3} \delta_{ij} \mu \frac{\partial U_k}{\partial x_k} \right), \quad (13)$$

$$\frac{D\rho}{Dt} + \frac{\partial (\rho \mathbf{K} \cdot \mathbf{U})_i}{\partial x_i} = 0, \quad (14)$$

$$\mathbf{K}^{ij} = \gamma \delta^{ij}, \quad (15)$$

where, γ is the volume porosity of the arterial wall and \mathbf{K} is the area porosity tensor, which is a symmetric second rank tensor. The momentum losses S_M are due to the permeability decrease, following the Darcy's law:

$$S_{M,i} = -\frac{\mu_{\text{plasma}}}{K_{\text{perm}}} U_i, \quad (16)$$

where, μ_{plasma} is the plasma viscosity, while K_{perm} is the Darcian permeability.

In the domain of the wall, all of the considered species concentrations are described by the modified convection-diffusion-reaction considering the porosity effects:

$$\gamma \frac{\partial c}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} ((\mathbf{K} \cdot \mathbf{U})_j c) = D \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \left(\mathbf{K} \cdot \frac{\partial c}{\partial x_j} \right) + S c, \quad (17)$$

where, c is the substance's concentration and D is the diffusivity.

The endothelial fluxes are defined by the Kedem-Katchalsky equations, which evaluate the fluxes through bio-membranes, based on the pressure and concentration differences across them [14], [15]. However, despite the fluxes of LDL and HDL, which are well described by the Kedem-Katchalsky equations, the endothelial monocyte and T-cell fluxes are described by experimental equations [14], [15]. The diffusive permeabilities of the LDL and HDL depend on the endothelium's nitric oxide concentration, which is also described by experimental equations [5], [16], [17].

All species are constrained with a zero-flux boundary condition to endothelial layer as well as, to the adventitia layer, except for the LDL and HDL concentrations in the adventitia layer, which are defined as fractions of the patient-specific blood concentrations. Moreover, all species have a zero-value initial concentration, except for the concentration of the contractile smooth muscle cells, which are a structural part of the arterial wall. The comorbid conditions of hypertension, diabetes and tachycardia were also considered in the plaque growth model [5], [9], [10], [18].

2.3.4 4th step – Arterial wall thickening & lumen narrowing

In the last step, the arterial wall thickening and lumen narrowing is evaluated using a linear stress-strain equation (as Eq. 7). Using the simulated species concentrations, we evaluate the volumetric strain distribution of the arterial wall, which is used as a global condition to the model. Frictionless support is applied as boundary condition to the adventitia and the arterial wall side areas. Using this approach, wall thickening is enabled by simulating the inward remodeling of the vascular wall (wall thickening).

2.4 Evaluation of the stenosis progression

The main metrics to describe atherosclerosis are the ECST and NASCET metrics, which are based on the measurement of the degree of narrowing of the lumen, to

calculate the degree of severity of the disease, and to decide its treatment strategy (Fig. 2). In our study, the NASCET method was implemented to evaluate the stenosis in the areas of plaque progression. In our approach, the average diameter of the selected sections was used in the NASCET equation for all cases.

Fig. 2 The NASCET and ECST equations

3. Results & Discussion

We reconstructed 5 carotid arteries, using the available MRI data, in order to be used as input to the plaque growth model. The mesh size and time-step were selected according to [5]. A simulation time period of 1 year was selected for all cases, while common patient parameters were used to result in a geometry-dependent problem, and therefore investigate properly the effect of plaque location on the progression of luminal stenosis. Finally, we extracted the NASCET values in the sections of maximum lumen stenosis progression as these resulted from each simulation.

Fig. 3 Luminal stenosis progression in area of curved arterial segment.

The resulted NASCET values are given in Table 1, indicating a strong correlation of plaque location to luminal stenosis progression. Specifically, the presence of atherosclerotic plaques in curved arterial segments may cause a higher luminal stenosis progression in the same arterial region, than in plaques located in straight arterial segments. This is justified by the large hemodynamic alteration which is caused by plaques in curved arterial segments, where lower endothelial shear stresses and blood recirculation appear, thus favoring the species infiltration within the arterial wall.

Table 1 Summarized progression of NASCET values and segment type

	CASE 1	CASE 2	CASE 3	CASE 4	CASE 5
NASCET progression	5.05%	20.75%	8.70%	12.6%	15.3%
Segment type	<i>straight</i>	<i>curved</i>	<i>straight</i>	<i>curved</i>	<i>curved</i>

Although the results confirm our assertion, however, the arterial cases of this study are limited to suggest a strong correlation of plaque location to luminal stenosis progression. Therefore, as a future work, this correlation will be examined to an extended dataset.

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References

- [1] J.-M. Cai, T. S. Hatsukami, M. S. Ferguson, R. Small, N. L. Polissar, and C. Yuan, "Classification of Human Carotid Atherosclerotic Lesions With In Vivo Multicontrast Magnetic Resonance Imaging," *Circulation*, vol. 106, no. 11, pp. 1368–1373, Sep. 2002, doi: 10.1161/01.CIR.0000028591.44554.F9.
- [2] W. J. Powers et al., "2018 Guidelines for the Early Management of Patients With Acute Ischemic Stroke: A Guideline for Healthcare Professionals From the American Heart Association/American Stroke Association," *Stroke*, vol. 49, no. 3, Mar. 2018, doi: 10.1161/STR.000000000000158.
- [3] P. Libby, "History of Discovery: Inflammation in Atherosclerosis," p. 15, 2013.
- [4] A. I. Sakellarios et al., "Modelling LDL accumulation in the case of endothelial dysfunction," vol. 5, no. 2, p. 11, 2011.
- [5] D. S. Pleouras et al., "Simulation of atherosclerotic plaque growth using computational biomechanics and patient-specific data," *Sci Rep*, vol. 10, no. 1, p. 17409, Dec. 2020, doi: 10.1038/s41598-020-74583-y.
- [6] M. Guo, Y. Cai, X. Yao, and Z. Li, "Mathematical modeling of atherosclerotic plaque destabilization: Role of neovascularization and intraplaque hemorrhage," *Journal of Theoretical Biology*, vol. 450, pp. 53–65, Aug. 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.jtbi.2018.04.031.
- [7] A. I. Sakellarios et al., "Prediction of Atherosclerotic Plaque Development in an In Vivo Coronary Arterial Segment Based on a Multilevel Modeling Approach," *IEEE Trans. Biomed. Eng.*, vol. 64, no. 8, pp. 1721–1730, Aug. 2017, doi: 10.1109/TBME.2016.2619489.
- [9] D. Pleouras et al., "Atherosclerotic Plaque Growth Prediction in Coronary Arteries using a Computational Multi-level Model: The Effect of Diabetes," in 2019 IEEE 19th International Conference on Bioinformatics and Bioengineering (BIBE), Athens, Greece, Oct. 2019, pp. 702–705. doi: 10.1109/BIBE.2019.00132.
- [10] D. Pleouras et al., "A computational multi-level atherosclerotic plaque growth model for coronary arteries," in 2019 41st Annual International Conference of the IEEE Engineering in Medicine and Biology Society (EMBC), Jul. 2019, pp. 5010–5013. doi: 10.1109/EMBC.2019.8857329.
- [8] A. Sakellarios et al., "Prediction of atherosclerotic disease progression using LDL transport modelling: a serial computed tomographic coronary angiographic study," *Eur Heart J Cardiovasc Imaging*, vol. 18, no. 1, pp. 11–18, Jan. 2017, doi: 10.1093/ehjci/jew035.
- [11] P. Siogkas et al., "Multiscale - Patient-Specific Artery and Atherogenesis Models," *IEEE Trans. Biomed. Eng.*, vol. 58, no. 12, pp. 3464–3468, Dec. 2011, doi: 10.1109/TBME.2011.2164919.
- [12] M. D. Mantzaris et al., "Computational modeling of atherosclerotic plaque progression in carotid lesions with moderate degree of stenosis *," in 2021 43rd Annual International Conference of the IEEE Engineering in Medicine & Biology Society (EMBC), Mexico, Nov. 2021, pp. 4209–4212. doi: 10.1109/EMBC46164.2021.9630376.
- [13] A. I. Sakellarios et al., "Prediction of Atherosclerotic Plaque Development in an In Vivo Coronary Arterial Segment Based on a Multilevel Modeling Approach," *IEEE Transactions on Biomedical Engineering*, vol. 64, no. 8, pp. 1721–1730, Aug. 2017, doi: 10.1109/TBME.2016.2619489.
- [14] M. Cilla, E. Peña, and M. A. Martínez, "Mathematical modelling of atheroma plaque formation and development in coronary arteries," *J. R. Soc. Interface*, vol. 11, no. 90, p. 20130866, Jan. 2014, doi: 10.1098/rsif.2013.0866.
- [15] A. I. Sakellarios, "Modelling LDL accumulation in the case of endothelial dysfunction," *Journal of the Serbian Society for Computational Mechanics*, vol. 5, pp. 90–100, 2011.
- [16] D. S. Pleouras et al., "A Novel Approach to Generate a Virtual Population of Human Coronary Arteries for In Silico Clinical Trials of Stent Design," *IEEE Open Journal of Engineering in Medicine and Biology*, vol. 2, pp. 201–209, 2021.